
WHAT EXTENSIVE READING IS, AND WHY IT IS A GOOD IDEA TO IMPLEMENT IT

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Abstract

The article reviews the body of research on extensive reading and briefly explains main benefits, such as learners' overall language development, automated lower-level skills of word recognition and parsing processes, increased vocabulary knowledge without direct vocabulary instruction, improved writing skills, increased motivation for learning languages, and confidence in reading. Using extensive reading persistently in reading courses creates few demands and challenges for the teacher and doesn't involve time-consuming lesson preparation.

Keywords: extensive reading, intensive reading, reading fluency, reading for pleasure.

Teaching young learners to read, oftentimes, the teacher focuses first on reading mechanics and word recognition, and once the necessary level of skill is achieved, young learners are engaged into in-class reading activities, where the teacher, while trying to further build their reading skills, also begins introducing them to strategies, that will allow students to read for particular information. This kind of reading is commonly known as reading to learn and intensive reading. While intensive reading is undeniably important, because its approaches and goals are well-aligned with the Common Core Standards, many researchers consider it crucial to always remember the simple idea, that the best way to learn to read is through reading. Students who read permanently and persistently, discover the pleasure of the process of reading, provided that they are free from the pressure of the lesson's tight timing and the looming after-reading tests (1).

R. Day emphasizes that reading is the interactive process, when readers use all sorts of their individual knowledge about the world and the language to build meaning (2). No two readers will draw identical conclusions about the same text, or have identical experience of reading the same book due to the differences in language proficiency, metalinguistic awareness, speed of cognitive processing, etc. So, reading needs to be given time and space to develop as a skill, and intensive reading-associated learning activities though being useful in their own way, can neither dramatically speed up or, moreover, replace this process. According to Day, such methods as grammar-translation method, or answering comprehension Qs, or discussing the content, though using reading as a part of the lesson, do not teach reading as such.

To briefly define extensive reading (ER), and to distinguish it from intensive reading (IR), we will address the abundant body of research available on the topic. Warning suggests an acronym 'READ' to point out the key characteristics of IR. It stands for 'reading quickly', 'enjoyability', 'adequate comprehension' and '(students) don't need a dictionary' (3). The factual rationale for the latter principle was provided in the study by Day, demonstrating that two groups of readers, with and without a dictionary showed no difference in text

comprehension, but it took the dictionary group twice longer to finish reading. Reading quickly requires fluency, whose development actually being one of the target skills of ER, can be ensured by choosing books of appropriate difficulty.

Discussing difficulty of books used for ER, all researchers are unanimous that they should be easy. This refers to Krashen's comprehension hypothesis that claims that comprehensible input is an inalienable for language development, and ER should comply with this requirement. To put the demand for comprehensible input in more definite terms, Day and Bamford suggested to base on Krashen's formula, where comprehensible input is (I+1), but instead of aiming for the zone of proximal development, subtract one level for the sake of reconsolidating already familiar language knowledge (4). Thus, for ER, comprehensible input will be at the learners' current level, or better, slightly below (i - 1) (5). In practice, learners can be taught to define their level independently by following a simple procedure: students should pick a book whose title appeals to them and read one page. If their reading speed is under 80 words per minute, and if they encounter more 2 unfamiliar words per page struggling with comprehension at the same time), then they must choose a book at an easier level. To make sure this level suits them, they are recommended to try another book at that level. They can also upgrade their level if the text feels too easy, but their main aim should be to feel comfortable while reading (3).

Simplicity of ER books is vital, because it is one of the things that build fluency. Among others is a thorough selection of reading materials, that should be purposefully written for students' level and contain a lot of high-frequency words and repetition (6). Higher lexical frequency increases the chances that the lexis will be learned and retained for longer. Unless a certain number of recurrent presentations of the word is ensured, it is likely that the word will not be retained even if form-meaning mapping was successful, and the students could fluently recognize it while reading. According to Day & Bamford, a sufficient repetition number is considerably higher than seven to nine times for long-term retention (4), which would look unnatural in not

adapted authentic texts, which lead to the conclusion that authentic texts cannot be used for ER.

Developing fluency allows readers to move away from word-by-word reading. Contrary to the common opinion that slow reading is more conscious reading that helps to enhance comprehension, reading slowly is poor reading. It may prevent information from reaching readers' long-term memory, which, in turn, may hinder information processing (6). Scanning, skimming, predicting by the topic, recognizing signal words are fluency strategies; being taught in-class, they will facilitate independent ER.

In terms of enjoyability, a chance to select a book one likes cannot be overestimated. The importance of providing language learners in ER programmes with the freedom to self-select materials has been highlighted by Grabe. Ateek refers to a study of 70 male EFL Saudi university students' reading speed, which demonstrated that those who self-selected their graded readers showed greater improvements in their reading speed than those who were assigned a text to read (1).

Speaking about adequate comprehension as one of the key characteristics of ER, it is important to mention that comprehension is a strategy-driven skill. Strategies are conscious behavior that needs to be taught through direct instruction, so IR provides a better context for strategy introduction. Nevertheless, being applied frequently enough, strategic behavior becomes automatic and turns into a skill. Research shows that consistently applying strategies helps students become better readers. This is the reason why many researchers promote the necessity to merge intensive and extensive approaches. For instance, Waring argues that ER is still often seen as supplemental to a main program, while it should be a core part of every language curriculum, and all language programs must have an ER component³. He urges that ER program should be aligned with the goals, aims and objectives of the school, otherwise, it will lack of direction. Thus, the key to a successful reading program is balancing course work with ER. Too much IR leads to not enough work on developing fluency. Too much ER prevents a learner from noticing certain language, and too much work only on reading skills and strategies will not develop the skill of reading. Insufficient work on vocabulary holds back fast development of reading skills (3).

ER and IR integration wise, one type of activities that can be applied to ER Timed Repeated Reading. It suits ER and IR lessons, but only under the condition that students read already familiar texts. They start from the beginning and read for one minute at a comfortable speed, after which they stop and underline the last word read. Then they go back to the beginning, read for another minute, stop and underline. The procedure is repeated several times. This helps to increase reading rate without urging students to read faster and enhances sight vocabulary, as increasingly rapid recognition of words in a text activates links between the graphic form and phonological information, links together appropriate semantic and syntactic resources, helps students to

recognise morphological affixation and access their mental lexicon (4).

Not needing a dictionary – the last principle postulated by Waring – is directly connected with learners' lexical knowledge and their strategic behavior, when they come across a new word. Some researchers argue that ER is mainly suited for reinforcing partially familiar words rather than building new vocabulary. Nevertheless, this does not exclude the learning and the acquisition of new vocabulary entirely (7). Day claims that the main benefit of old vocabulary reinforcement is learning new meanings of familiar words, and thus, expanding their semantic fields and learning new collocations. Brown et al. cite Horst, Cobb and Meara who claimed that through extensive reading learners can "enrich their knowledge of the words they already know, increase lexical access speeds, build network linkages between words, and...a few words will be acquired (4)". Waring agrees that the percentage of new vocabulary retention in ER tends to be close to insignificant, and concludes that for the purpose of learning new words, a massive amount of graded reading is needed (7) - Day calls the number of 60-70 books per term. Vocabulary learning is a cumulative process and further encounters with the words would reinforce acquisition (8).

In terms of both fluency and enjoyability, as well as improving vocabulary knowledge, simultaneous extensive reading and listening to the same story should be mentioned. Its benefits are many: it helps to increase overall language proficiency, in particular listening comprehension. Comprehension improves due to facilitated correct phrasing, that students can achieve by simply following the prosody of presenter's speech. Young learners are especially prone either to read word-by-word or to break sentences into small incoherent parts, which distorts the meaning, so for them an audio model is particularly crucial. The teacher reading aloud performs this function best, but out of class, hearing the text they are trying to read will definitely help them to unite syntactic segments and will eventually lead to better comprehension.

Also, reading-while-listening proved to be more effective than the reading-only in terms of new vocabulary acquisition. In addition, lower decay of word-retention was noticed in postponed after-reading tests (4).

Reading-while-listening was described as the most comfortable by the majority of students due to the fact that was that segmenting of the text was done by the narrator through intonation. As a result, learners did not have to invest so much into focusing on syntax, and had enough spare working-memory space to better process the content. This, in turn, allowed them to make better inferences to deduce the meanings of unfamiliar words (9).

As Day argues, and all his claims find support in research on ER, ER has many benefits, some of which we have already discussed above. First, gains in overall language development, which was directly or indirectly supported by several studies of ER programs. Day

³ Waring, R. 2011. Extensive Reading in English Teaching. In Widodo, H. & A. Cirocki (Eds.) Innovation and

notes that this is an incidental benefit, which does not diminish its significance.

Second, students become readers; more specifically, ER contributes to automatising the lower-level skills of word recognition and parsing processes (10).

Third, increased vocabulary knowledge without direct vocabulary instruction.

Fourth, improved writing skills due to enhanced visual input and availability of multiple revisions of written samples.

And finally, better attitudes and increased motivation for learning languages, as well as renewed confidence in reading. One of basic principles of ER is to read for pleasure, which might translate into general proficiency improvement and an increase in reading motivation. Most importantly, the incidental nature of language learning-related benefits of ER creates very few specific demands for the teacher (11) and requires nearly zero lesson preparation.

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